

CURRENT STATE OF RESEARCH ON THE DEVELOPMENT METHODOLOGY OF CO-CREATED PRODUCTS AND PRODUCTS WITH PERSONALITY

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Abstract: Numerous methodologies have been developed over time to improve the design of products in order to fulfill the wishes and expectations of customers, but so far none of these methodologies has been directly contributing to the design process of products ensuring guaranteed success. This is difficult to achieve due to various aspects related to the human personality that is influenced by one's own life experience, the process of transposing characteristics of human personality to a product in the design and anticipating how the market will evolve, given the socio-economical context. Although input from consumers about how they relate to a product's personality is important, the influence of personality on purchasing preferences and how they interact is only a basis for designers and manufacturers to help them approach the consumer's desire, without knowing with certainty their desire or whether the product will be successful or not. In this situation, more research is necessary to attain the design of a generally valid methodology for a wide variety of products.

Keywords: product with personality, co-created products, design, emotions, methodology

Introduction

The methodology is a general research strategy that highlights how to use the methods that define the means of data collection or how it is recommended to calculate a result [Howell K. E., 2013]. Specifically, methodology is the design process for researching or developing a procedure without it being a tool, method, or procedure.

With the rapid evolution of technology, market competition has also increased, leading to a different perspective on the final purpose of the design process. Thus, attention gradually shifted from the interest in the product and the producer, to the interest in the customer and his degree of satisfaction [Anderson, 1990]. The competitive environment has brought a series of changes for both producers and customers, increasing the attention and involvement of both parties in terms of market demands and offers. Moreover, customer-made design has replaced manufacturer-made design, while customer satisfaction has become a focal point [Gitman and Carl, 2005].

The primary goal of designers and manufacturers is to increase customer satisfaction, and to do this we need to reduce the gap "between what the customer really needs (customer requirements) and what the manufacturer can provide (product specifications)" [Koomsap, 2011]. Mass production, which involves the production of a large volume of products with a wide range of prices, quality and use, describes a type of design that cannot satisfy all customers and involves a procedure based on transforming customer needs and requirements into product specifications.

1. Definition and classification of co-creation methodologies

Risdiyono and Pisut Koomsap [Risdiyono, Koomsap, 2011] have developed a concept that has the role of better responding to customer needs. They claim that every customer can be considered a designer, because they are pursuing the goal of fulfilling their need. To do this, they take into account the first image designed in the mind that can be materialized using words, sketches, drawings, prototypes, which are then translated into specifications, features or functions of future products.

Risdiyono and Pisut Koomsap define the "concept of customer participation" (CIDP) which is a stage in the production process in which the customer is involved and can take part in creating value. It can be positioned at the end of the process, in mass production, which means the customer does not have the opportunity to participate before the product reaches its

final shape. Or it could be positioned before the assembly stage, to provide a greater variety of products to customers. [Risdiyono, Koomsap, 2011]

Fig.1.Example of mass production products with a variety of options for customers [1]

Fig.2 Example of products that are customized by consumers [2]

By introducing and placing a new CIDP (customer involvement decoupling point) at the beginning of the value chain, an additional channel will be created through which customers are involved in the design. Thus, a real individual personalization will be obtained.

The concept of customer design (DFC) is the process by which customers are not fully integrated in the design process. They either contribute to the selection of the final product (mass production) or select and combine different parts (mass customization)

DBC (design by customer) is a new concept designed to actively involve consumers in any stage that makes up the value chain, being encouraged to define the most appropriate alternative that meets cost and requirements through the capabilities of a manufacturing company. This concept is based on the idea that needs and constraints are best known to customers. The manufacturer has the task to respond to customers who have a personal need and implicitly require a

dedicated product, as well as take care to ensure a dynamic flow of products. DBC offers customers the most important role in defining the specifications of the final product [Risdiyono, Koomsap, 2011].

The study involved a process of sorting customers based on their needs and preferences allowing manufacturers to attract a larger market by integrating customized and personalized mass products.

Fig.3.Example of a highly customizable product [3]

According to the analysis, by identifying a set of important attributes of the product, they can be derived from the design process itself: (1) utilitarian design - focuses on the practical benefits that a product can offer such as durability, effectiveness, reliability and multifunctionality; (2) ergonomic design - highlights the way the user interacts with the product being focused on comfort and ease of use; (3) visual design - driven by shape, color, size and desire to attract the consumer without interacting with the product.

The Kano model was developed in 1984 by Professor Noriaki Kano, being recognized as an effective tool dedicated to relating the characteristics of the product to customer satisfaction. Over time, it has managed to attract the attention of many designers and researchers involved in projects aimed at developing products and services [Mikulić, 2007], focusing on differentiating the characteristics of the product. Despite the fact that the Kano model is classified into five categories and a dysfunctional value, many researchers mention only three of them. Thus, according to the method, the attributes of any product can be classified into six categories as follows:

1. Basic / expected characteristics (must be - M) - represent basic characteristics that a product must have, and the relationship between the perceived performance of the product and customer satisfaction is non-linear and asymmetric. Thus, the low level of fulfillment of these characteristics leads to customer dissatisfaction, being basic characteristics that reflect the quality expected by him. [Lina He et al. 2017]. Their very name indicates that they must be complied with in order for the product to enter the market.

2. Performance characteristics (one-dimensional - O) - represents the characteristics that lead to satisfaction when they are met, and to dissatisfaction when they are not present, with customer satisfaction being proportional to their degree of fulfillment. They can be requested by the customer representing important characteristics of the product quality. [Sauerwein et al. 1996] Thus, a box of natural juice that says it has 20% more fruit pulp will lead to customer satisfaction, and if it has only 10% the customer will be dissatisfied and feel misled. [103]

3. Lovely features (attractive - A) - these features are unpredictable by the customer, providing satisfaction when fully achieved, but do not cause dissatisfaction when not met. Their role is to stimulate the imagination of a potential consumer, being used to help the customer discover needs that they have not thought about until now. [103] They have the greatest influence on customer satisfaction through a product, not being explicitly expressed or expected. [Sauerwein

et al. 1996] Moreover, the engineer has the role of inferring this "unknown need", which offers a significant competitive advantage.

4. Characteristics of indifference (indifferent - I) - these characteristics cannot be considered as good or bad, and do not have the ability to lead the client to the feeling of satisfaction or dissatisfaction. [Lina He et al. 2017]. For example, the wall thickness of an aluminum carbonated beverage container could be a key element in the design process, while the consumer will not notice the differences between the containers.

5. Reverse characteristics (reverse - R) - these quality characteristics lead to dissatisfaction when they are met and to a high degree of satisfaction when they are not met [Mikulić, 2007]. These features are important because not all customers want high-tech features for their products, preferring the basic version of it.

Questionable value (questionable -Q) - Occurs in the use of a survey involving questionnaires with a structure consisting of two questions, while the answers indicate a misunderstanding of the questions or the presence of an error in the answer to a question [Latta, 2019].

Kano's model illustrates the first five characteristics presented above, and their positioning according to the degree of customer satisfaction or dissatisfaction, and the degree of functionality or lack of functionality of the product.

Kano has also developed a methodology that helps map the answers consumers provide during the survey. It uses: basic, performance, delightful and indifferent requirements can be classified by means of a questionnaire, so that for each feature of the product, a pair of questions is formulated to which the consumer can answer in five different ways. [Sauerwein et al. 1996].

The questionable value (questionable - Q) appears when the questionnaire contains questions related to a series of technical solutions of a product. This often leads to an inability to understand the question from the part of the respondent. This is because a client is not interested in how to solve a problem, but what is the problem that will be fixed. [Sauerwein et al. 1996]

The two answers obtained are combined and listed in a table being noted according to the five characteristics: basic (M), performance (O), attractiveness (A), indifference (I), reverse (R) and questionable (Q). The first four features are intuitive, while category R is unstable and Q indicates a questionable result .[Gupta, Srivastava, 2011]

Among the methods developed to provide a better understanding of customer needs are the Kano model and the QFD, being widely adopted to contribute to product development and increase competitiveness [Ji, Jin, Wang and Chen, 2014]

A research study conducted by Lina He and collaborators proposes to improve the Kano model by implementing quality functions (QFD) to obtain an optimized version of the Kano model, called Kano model with importance frequency (IF-Kano) with the ultimate goal of integrating the latter in QFD. IF-Kano was developed to identify the Kano category of each customer requirement based on the frequency of mention and the share of customer requirements [Lina He et al. 2017]. The model aims to determine the appropriate Kano categories for customer requirements and target values of technical characteristics in order to obtain an optimal design solution with the best balance between the satisfaction of the producing company and client satisfaction [Lina He și colab. 2017].

For the application of the Kano method to be fundamental to an efficient design process, the way in which the classification of customer requirements is developed must highlight both the consumer's perception, and the capacity and potential of the manufacturer [Xu et al., 2009]. This is also the role of QFD: to achieve a balance between the two components of a cost-effective design process.

The study conducted by Lina He is based on the IF-Kano model, which provides a set of criteria for classifying customer requirements given the interaction between frequency and importance [Lina He et al. 2017]. The IF-Kano classification mapped to the four areas of Kano characteristics: attractive characteristics (A), followed by performance characteristics (O), basic characteristics (M) and indifference characteristics (I). With IF-Kano (I-importance, F-frequency), each customer requirement can be represented as a point of two coordinates (I belongs to X, F belongs to Y), C_i , where C represents the requirement and i is the normalized importance (weight).

Because consumer requirements in Kano's feature categories have a different impact on satisfaction, the IF-Kano can increase the designer's understanding of these requirements and help make decisions in the design process. Moreover, the IF-Kano model was integrated into the QFD, thus obtaining a high degree of optimization. This is done by translating the requirements from the consumer into engineering characteristics, determining a number of benefits for both parties [Lina He et al. 2017].

Following the study developed by Lina He and her collaborators, it was concluded that the developed IF-Kano model defines a set of logical classification criteria for Kano categories, allowing the quantitative measurement of customer requirements. However, designing and positioning the product on the market is a difficult task, as the market is not shaped by a narrow range of needs, but is increasingly segmented. Thus, it is concluded that the IF-Kano method can help in the strategic selection of a series of micro-segments, which has the same Kano classification scheme, resulting in a profit that benefits both the manufacturer and the customer. On the other hand, customer needs can be latent and difficult to describe, all the more so as there is a risk that they will not be well informed about the variety of products and aspects related to product costs and characteristics [Lina He et al. 2017].

All these aspects can lead to the alteration of the design and manufacturing process of the product and, implicitly, can influence its delivery, cost and quality. It is recommended to initiate multiple interactions with customers and guide them during the design process. The methodologies presented are an important step in terms of consumer involvement in production processes and in order to create benefits for producers and designers, as well as for consumers. By integrating consumers, a relationship is created between them, which is a source of information for potential customers: they communicate openly and exchange honest opinions based on a user's own experience with the product.

By approaching the principles of co-creation, the producer ends up saving time and resources by researching the market and making studies on the needs and expectations of potential customers. Thus, by encouraging the consumer to actively participate in all creative processes, starting from the researching stage, the configuration of products and services, all the way up to their consumption, companies obtain a set of important information from customers that they use to meet their needs. [Prahalad, Ramaswamy, 2004].

A perspective based on direct collaboration with the user is much more important than focusing exclusively on the product, because this collaboration brings benefits to both parties: the manufacturer creates and brings to market products that meet customer needs, and the consumer buys a product that meets their needs.

2. Definition and classification of methodologies of personality products

The personality of the products arose from the human personality, and a number of characteristics of the human personality were attributed to the products. Pascale Govers draws our attention in her doctoral dissertation entitled "Product Personality" [Govers, 2004] to the fact that "An important difference between human personality and product personality is that the personality of the product is more explicitly linked to the outside of the product", as opposed to that of the human being, which is strongly anchored in a set of inner principles, behaviors, and beliefs. Thus, while internal qualities are guided by the human personality, the personality of the product guides a number of external qualities [Govers, 2004].

If at the dawn of the first industrialized production, the designers were concerned with the functionality of the product, nowadays they dedicate their resources to finding efficient methods in terms of attracting the user to products through their personality. Thus, the quality of life will be improved and the environment will be protected from excessive and uncontrolled consumption of products, and the emergence of a product on the market will be an opportunity to interact with the user/beneficiary both during the selection and purchase process, as well as during the use of the product. Research shows that the personality of the product has a direct influence on the choice made by the buyer, but also on his general preferences. In essence, for consumers, products with personality are objects that can be associated with their image [Belk 1988, Sirgy 1982].

There are different methods of assessing human personality. They are classified into: projective methods, subjective methods and psychometric methods. In the framework of projective methods, people are required to interpret an abstract role, so it is assumed that through this interpretation, the personality of the individual is revealed. Subjective methods involve therapeutic interviews in which topics related to one's own perception of the world are

discussed, thus providing information about one's personality [Carver & Scheier, 1996; Pervin 1975]. In the case of the psychometric assessment of personality, standard questionnaires such as human personality measurement scales are used. [Carver & Scheier, 1996].

Govers and Mugge [Govers, Mugge, 2004] conducted a study aimed at analyzing the correlation between a person's personality and that of their product, more precisely, "the personality congruence theory". The results of the study showed that stronger attachments were created to products that had a personality congruent with the personality of the owner. Moreover, this suggests that designers have the ability to stimulate attachment to the product by designing objects that have a number of characteristics behind which hides a predetermined personality compatible with the characteristics of the user's personality [Goves, Mugge, 2004].

Self-matching products are those products that create compatibility between the personality of the buyer and that of the product, and may have an appearance similar to that of a self-concept of the buyer. Moreover, they believe that "product-personality congruence influences the experience attachment to a product" based on the following hypothesis: high congruence between product and personality results in a higher degree of attachment to product, rather than low congruence between product and personality. [Govers, Mugge, 2004].

This study uses the scenario strategy, presenting a hypothetical situation in which a series of specific circumstances are proposed, thus allowing the study of processes that take place over a long period of time and are focused on topics of interest. In this case, respondents are presented with a color image of a product after which they are informed of the scenario in which the personality of a hypothetical person is described. Moreover, to cover the subject of high congruence and low congruence, the personality of the product may or may not be similar to that of the character in the script. Thus, Govers argues that agreeableness, extroversion, and conscientiousness were considered to be three of the five dimensions of human personality relevant to products as well [Govers, Mugge, 2004; Govers 2004].

Goves and Mugge [Govers, Mugge, 2004] conducted two pre-tests to verify whether the personality of personal stimuli is perceived as intentional, and to choose a product with congruent and incongruent stimuli. Thus, the congruence is represented by a match between the consumer's personality and that of the product, and the incongruity signifies the lack of this compatibility.

In the second pre-test, five colored images with toasters were presented in order to identify the stimulants. 92 respondents took part in the test and they evaluated a toaster taking into consideration the three personality dimensions: pleasantness, extroversion and conscientiousness [Govers, Mugge, 2004]. The toaster number two obtained the highest average of the extroversion features, and toaster number four obtained the highest average of the features of conscientiousness.

The study includes the personality of the person (extroverted/conscientious) and the personality of the product (extroverted/conscientious). It involved 180 respondents belonging to a group of household consumers [Govers, Mugge, 2004].

After this stage, it was suggested to verify the way in which the conditions were perceived by another test. It consists of the personality of the extroverted/conscientious person and the personality of the extroverted/conscientious product, along with a written description and images of the two toasters. To measure the congruence between the products and the personality of the consumers, four items were employed using five points. The results obtained indicate an interaction between the personality of the person and the product.

Thus, the high congruence between the consumer's personality and the personality of the product is considered to lead to a higher degree of attachment. This aspect was verified by another test in which respondents read about the extroverted person and the presentation of the extroverted toaster. As a result, they predicted a high degree of attachment, compared to those to whom the conscientious toaster was presented. The same thing resulted from the group of respondents who read the other scenario of the conscientious person.

Following this study, it was concluded that people become more attached to products with a personality similar to their own, an aspect mentioned in the literature [Govers, Mugge, 2004; Jordan, 1997; Aaker, 1999; Govers and Schoormans 2005; Kleine et al., 1995; Dumitrescu, 2013] as a relationship of high congruence between product and personality. This is because people tend to associate their image with products in order to stand out, so the product

acquires a symbolism for its owner. Moreover, the attachment to the product leads to an increase in sustainability by extending its lifespan. Thus, increasing the attachment to the product contributes to a sustainable society. However, the authors point out a number of limitations to this study. These include results based only on toasters and the involvement of only two dimensions of the human personality. [Govers, Mugge, 2004]

Pascal Govers conducts a study [Govers, 2004] in which he analyzes the relationship between the personality of the product and its appearance and how designers “use the appearance of products as a tool to create products that express something” [Govers, 2004]. The study examines the possibility that designers can create a product with a specific personality that is identified and recognized by consumers. Thus, 88 respondents with an average age of 48 years were randomly selected, and 18 graduates in the field created sketches with clothes irons that have a personality characteristic that can be applied to both people and products: happy, cute or harsh. They were created on the basis of an instructional image of a prototype ironer with certain functions.

Nine sketches were randomly selected which the respondents evaluated, and then measured using a five-point evaluation scale (1 = not cute / not happy / not harsh and 5 = happy / cute / harsh). A group average was calculated for the three categories corresponding to a characteristic.

The results show that the “harsh” irons have a high score both individually and in the group, while the group characterized by the adjective “cute” obtained the lowest score.

Averages obtained per group and individually for the main characteristics of the clothes irons [Govers, 2004]

To determine whether respondents recognized the personality of the product based on the characteristic used as a basis in the design process, a repeated ANOVA measurement was performed. The results showed that the clothes irons belonging to the characteristic - "happy", are perceived significantly happier ($M = 3.11$) compared to the other categories of cute irons ($M = 2.80$, $F(1,87) = 10.3$, $p < .05$), harsh irons ($M = 2.63$, $F(1,87) = 21.3$, $p < .001$), while irons belonging to the cute feature ($M = 2.41$) are perceived significantly nicer than the harsh ones ($M = 1.94$, $F(1,87) = 18.5$, $p < 0.001$).

The results show that the clothes irons classified according to the harsh characteristic are evaluated by the respondent as being harsher ($M = 3.76$) than the nice clothes irons ($M = 2.57$), $F(1,87) = 98.5$, $p < 0.001$ and happy clothes irons ($M = 2.88$), $F(1,87) = 63.4$, $p < 0.001$

The questionnaires of the students who made the sketches of the models were then analyzed, and they indicated that for the product designed as happy, round, light shapes were used. Moreover, it was associated with bright colors such as yellow, orange and red. The cute feature-designed clothes irons involve round, sturdy, compact shapes associated with warm colors, while students who designed harsh irons used sturdy, large shapes and sharp, dark colors (blue, green, gray).

The conclusion of the study is that people recognize the characteristic of "harshness", the respondents perceive it correctly, but an uncertain result was obtained in terms of nice and happy characteristics because the two are somewhat similar.

Methods that focus on identifying consumer personality traits that can be reflected in the appearance and interaction with products are an important step in ensuring the success of the product. By understanding the mechanisms of meeting the emotional needs of the consumer in relation to the product, both the designer and the manufacturer will collaborate effectively, easily achieving their common goal of bringing successful products to market. Thus, the working time will be reduced, the work efficiency will increase and in the end, the consumer is satisfied and will recommend the product to other people who have a personality similar to his own. The methods that will involve as many characteristics of the human personality will determine a greater success by covering a variety of human typologies, and thus a product can be placed on the market in several variants leaving the buyer free to choose.

If the consumer is surprised through a pleasant interaction with the product that stimulates their curiosity and puts them in a certain mood, this leads to the increase of the success for the product.

The complexity of the world in which we live with a multitude of products to satisfy a wide range of needs of the modern man is overwhelming. Methodologies that aim to identify the personality traits of consumers in order to translate them into the image and interaction of a product are important for the development of new products. Specifically, they help to improve the way designers rely on their intuition and anticipation of the desires of consumers. Users' expectations for how to interact with products have increased greatly in the last decade, with the rapid evolution of technology, as the products have become increasingly intelligent and captivating.

The concept of product personality is an important tool in the process of designing durable goods [Jordan 2002]. Specifically, determining the personality of a product represents on a small scale the success of the manufacturer, and on a large scale, it increases the quality of life by preventing uncontrolled consumption, wasting a large volume of energy and protecting the environment. As early as 1989, in one of the best-selling books called "The End of Nature", Bill McKibben sounded the alarm for the future, stating, "By changing climate, we make every place on earth artificial."

Methods of designing products with personality lead to an emotional connection with the user. The latter will determine the attachment to the product, and then, to the total diminution of the user's desire to replace the functional product with a new one, or to give it up when it fails. Thus, the consumer will look for solutions to prolong the life of the product, through its consecutive repair, and a new purchase will be postponed. Such a strategy can encourage responsible behavior and consumer education that can be promoted over time and passed on to future generations. Specifically, an educated consumer will attract other consumers. Their own conviction and satisfaction will determine the people in his environment to buy a product that reflects their personality.

The market offers a multitude of products that meet a wide range of needs and requirements, while technological progress is growing. The consumer becomes increasingly disoriented in the face of a variety of new products [Govers, 2004]. Not knowing how and what to choose, they will be guided by the advertisement and the price, and depending on his budget, the impact of advertising and personal beliefs, they will decide which product to buy. Research on the elements that influence the buyer's decision reveals the importance of the appearance of the product and how the user interacts with it. Moreover, it was found that the two criteria mentioned above are closely related to the personality of the product, and the key to the consumer's determination to purchase a particular product is the congruence between his personality and that of the product. Much of this research aims to study human behavior and less the concern for its application in the design process.

3. General conclusions

Symbolic significance contributes to making a decision about a product, and for companies it is the way in which they differentiate their product from those on the market. Thus, it is vital to create a design methodology that includes principles of the co-creation process and the involvement of product personality characteristics. [Govers, 2004]

Based on the research conducted in this paper, I consider that the most important methods are the Kano method and the QFD method, because they can be used together increasing their efficiency and being useful in developing co-created products. These methods help identify and meet the needs and requirements consumers have, and the direct contribution that customers have.

The most important detailed methodologies for developing personality products are the script method and the psychometric method for determining the personality of products, because they confront the consumer with images and scenarios, based on which they must infer the product personality (image) or its correlation with the product (scenario). These are useful because they are tools used by designers for collecting important information from the client, enabling the designer to come closer to their perception.

The methodologies presented bring a number of benefits for both the manufacturer (these correctly identify customer requirements and needs, classify the importance of product features for the customer, solicit customer feedback, more sales, less wasted time, faster company growth, market recognition) and for the buyer (high degree of satisfaction, increase of self-esteem due to their own contribution to the product, the market provides products that really meet their needs, they are no longer disoriented due to the varied number of products).

4. Research directions

Following the elaboration of this paper, it was concluded that these will be the new research directions:

1. Development of combined methods for making co-created products and products with personality
2. Development of tools, methods and mechanisms that can be applied by consumers, customers, buyers
3. Development of mathematical models associated with these combined methods
4. Carrying out case studies to validate the methods and models designed

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